

**SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ELECTRONIC FORM OF
EDUCATION USING "INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION
TECHNOLOGIES" UNDER THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBAL
DIGITALIZATION.**

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Annatation.

The article examines the use of information and communication technologies in the education system in the context of the rapid development of information processes in the world. Using e-learning resources when using information and communication technologies in traditional education, using effective teaching methods such as online learning courses, distance learning, mobile learning, e-learning. Online educational resources are widely used in teaching full-time and part-time students, self-study, and advanced training.

Key words.

Blended education, information and communication technology, online education, self-directed learning, distance learning, e-learning.

While informatization processes in the world are developing at a tremendous speed, the use of information and communication technologies in the education system has become an urgent need. Effective use of information and communication technologies and the use of electronic educational resources in traditional education.

Online learning courses, distance learning, mobile learning, e-learning are used as teaching methods, which are widely used and effective in Russia, Europe and Korea. Online educational resources are widely used in teaching full-time and part-time students, independent students, advanced training.

As a result of the use of electronic educational resources using information and communication technologies in traditional education, the concept of blended learning (Blended Learning) was created in modern education. Blended learning [1,3] - the student receives new knowledge from the teacher and online resources.

In this case, the student will be able to control the pace, time and quality of knowledge.

The blended learning system can be used in corporate training of schoolchildren, students, employees and various trainings.

In blended learning, the student first learns new knowledge from the teacher in the classroom, and after training improves and consolidates his knowledge by doing homework using electronic resources.

Teachers can assign students labs, seminar quizzes, topic questions, or self-study on a topic as homework. Internet resources, in turn, are enriched with control questions that track students' knowledge, control the pace and quality of student learning.

Here are the pros and cons of blended learning:

Students have a number of benefits for learning using online learning resources:

1. A student voluntarily begins to study on an educational resource. The student develops self-control, striving for the goal;

2. The student can study at a convenient time and in convenient conditions. He can learn new knowledge and professions with the help of online courses, without going anywhere for additional knowledge.

All you need is a computer and the Internet;

3. Students' learning is accelerated through training courses created on the basis of multimedia (video, audio, animation) elements, this technology is especially effective for intensive study of foreign languages;

Disadvantages of blended education:[2,89]

1. Students, independent learners do not have the skills to use an online educational resource;

2. Lack of opportunities for students to use online courses. There is not enough computer or the Internet is not connected;

3. Teachers, educators do not have sufficient knowledge on the creation and use of courses;

4. Lack of programmers who create software for online educational resources and specialists who accompany them.

Suggestions and recommendations. We believe that in order to address the above shortcomings, it is necessary to provide adequate funding for the necessary technical support and professional guidance for staff and students.

In a word, blended learning is considered a priority direction of learning in modern educational conditions and creates unlimited opportunities for teachers and students. Blended learning allows you to optimize the teacher's teaching time and increase the effectiveness of teaching.

At the same time, the student becomes an active participant in the educational process and has the opportunity to form an individual educational trajectory based on their needs. This is a great help in preparing competitive professionals in today's environment. In these wet days, when globalization and climate change threaten the future of mankind, most of our students and knowledge-hungry young people stay at home and receive blended (distance) learning, it will not be an exaggeration if they effectively use elements of education and e-learning and develop learning.

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